

CANINE BRUCELLOSIS DUE TO *B. CANIS* – OUTBREAK MANAGEMENT

In order to avoid or reduce the spread of *B. canis* certain immediate measures should be taken until the definitive diagnosis is obtained.

After positive diagnosis is confirmed, there are management options that should be considered, further epidemiological investigations that should be carried out as well as further testing of epidemiologically linked dogs. Equally important is to appropriately communicate the findings, raise awareness on the presence of *B. canis* in the area so that relevant biosecurity measures could be activated. These options were put together by a panel of scientists from partner countries. In reality the practical management of cases will vary according to factors including the prevalence of disease, level of risk presented, the risk appetite of the owners, veterinarians and authorities involved, the resources available and local policies and regulations.

